

International Journal of Human Resource & Industrial Research (IJHRIR)

ISSN: 2349 –3593 (Online), ISSN: 2349 –4816 (Print)

Email: editor@arseam.com

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TOWARDS STRESS MANAGEMENT: STRESS AND ITS EFFECT ON HUMAN RECOURSE

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Abstract

Stress in the place of work is an increasingly hot matter, as employers are positioned with the greater responsibility of handling stressed staff. Employees are subjected to a greater degree of stress while they attempt to enhance their human competencies in order to have an edge in the highly challenging global condition. Organizations concentrate on growing productivity. Technology allows us to do things faster and on a much better scale, but it also raises expectations of a rapid response and the accessibility of individuals to interact to meet business needs. This provides both opportunities and challenges for HR to influence how an organization makes best use of its human and organizational resources, without jeopardizing employee comfort and a sense of equality or “organizational justice.”

In this respect, I define Management of Stress and deal with the pathology or evaluating functions of Productivity and Human Resources. Finally, the hypotheses that Management of stress, can play an important role in Productivity and promote of Human Recourses.

Key Words: *Employees, Human Recourses, productivity, Stress, Stress Management.*

1. Introduction

A Canadian psychologist Hans Seyle, the founder of the theory of stress, defined stress “as the nonspecific response of our body to any demand for change” (cited in Le Fevre et al., 2003, pp.726-744). Looker and Gregson (2003) describe stress as the mismatch between perceived demands and the perceived abilities to cope. Additionally, stress has been simply described as an unavoidable consequence of life (Sorenson, 2007). Nel (2005) explains that stress is necessary for people to be successful. Exposure to stress over a period of time can be a stimulus for growth in a certain area. People have to find their own balance to decrease the risk of the effects of ongoing stress. Looker and Gregson (2003) note that “...people live and work most of the time under stress so these feelings are familiar to them and they do not pay any attention to them” (p.70). In other words, we do not notice the signs of stress or we do not connect them with stress. Johnson (2005, p.22) gives a good example, quoting an interviewee who says resignedly: “Life is to be endured, not enjoyed”. Furthermore, Cunningham (1997, p.171) warns: “Burnout is as much a result of the inability to take in new energy as it is the inability to let out negative energy and stagnation”. The results of our research have not revealed any such consequences. Cunningham (1997) proposes that stress needs to be optimized, because too little stress can be as harmful as too much of it. They lead to apathy, boredom and loss of interests and cause rustout as the other pole of burnout. Both are caused by distress due to too little or too much burdening. But Le Fevre et al. (2003, p.734) believe that management must not seek to manage stress to an optimal level, much less induce stress in their employees, as part of any endeavour to increase performance: “There would appear to be little or no evidence in the occupational stress literature to support the assertion that a reasonable amount of stress, pressure, or anxiety in the workplace leads to high performance. We suggest therefore, that it may be time to explicitly reject this stance.” Among organizational measures Treven (2005) recommends the application of control

Strategies over factors causing stress and various programs for employees to manage stress (workshops on stress management, workshops on relaxing methods, etc.). Organizations are also suggested to create a favorable organizational climate, set strategies of planning and developing careers, as well as motivating employees. As Donaldson-Feilder et al. (2008, p.11) say, managers act as “gatekeepers” to their employees' exposure to stressful working conditions and are vital to the identification and management of stress in the workplace. This means that managers need to understand what behaviours they should show in order to manage their employees in a way that minimizes work-related stress. As suggested by Ivancevich et al. (2008, p.240), managers could take certain actions to create a supportive work environment. For example, they could set an example by being a source of support for subordinates. They could encourage open communication and maximum exchange of information. Next they could provide subordinates with timely performance feedback, presented in an encouraging, nonthreatening manner. Further they could provide for mentoring of the less experienced by more senior members of the work group. They could also work to maintain and increase work group cohesion.

2.1 The Effects of Stress?

Causes leading to job stress usually consist of inappropriate work environment such as narrow and congested workplace, poor ventilation system, disturbing noise while working, job overload, unclear or vague job role and responsibilities, poor relationship among colleagues, lots of rules and regulations, lack of career growth opportunity, including the nature of work itself which maybe too risky or tiresome. All of these can give rise to stress.

Selye, the father of stress (1974) divided stress into two stressors as follows: 1.Negative stress or distress means the individual experiences negative emotions as anxiety or worry perhaps upon retiring. Physical effects may follow such as headaches or diarrhea. Positive stress or eustress pertains to an exciting event stimulating a person to feel glad or happy as a bride, before the marriage ceremony. She is so happy and she cannot sleep.

2.Negative stress also causes economic and social losses, especially for businesses. These losses come from ineffective work due to sickness which decreases both time at work and profit. Furthermore, people who suffer from negative stress often apply ineffective methods to seek release from it such as drinking, smoking, taking drugs, and shopping. Some employees have indulged themselves in gambling, and some have committed suicide (Mehri, 2000)

Stress has a positive side called eustress that is less well-known and less frequently used in colloquial language. Eustress or “good stress” refers to a psychological response to a stressor that is interpreted as having positive implications for well-being, according to Selye (1983). Distress and eustress represent distinct constructs and are not at opposite ends of a continuum (i.e., the lack of distress does not indicate the presence of eustress; (Quick, 1997).

According to Simmons (2000), positive stress and negative stress cannot be definitely separated. They are mixed together like water in a bathtub. Positive stress is like cold water whereas negative stress is like hot water. When hot and cold water is filled into a bathtub it will be combined and the water temperature will be determined by the quantity of hot and cold water. Also Simmon found eustress consists of positive affect, meaningfulness , manageability, and hope. Distress consists of negative affect, job alienation, anxiety, and anger/hostile.

2.2Job Satisfaction

An employee satisfaction inventory (ESI) was found to be an important tool to measure job satisfaction and employee' physical and mental health (Koustelios and Bagiatis 1997)

Psychologist and management consultant Frederick Herzberg developed the two factor theory of motivation. The two factors are hygiene and motivator factors. Herzberg's study comes from a group of 200 accountants and engineers. Herzberg and Synderman (1959) concluded that,

1.Extrinsic conditions, namely pay, status, job security, working conditions, fringe benefits, policies and interpersonal relations do not positively influence worker motivation, but enable the worker to avoid dissatisfaction with the work.

2.Intrinsic conditions, namely feelings of achievement, experiencing meaningful work, opportunities for advancement, recognition, and opportunities to grow, influence the motivation of employees to work hard because they bring satisfaction to the workers.

2.3 Cross culture Management

One of the most widely referenced approaches for analyzing variables among cultures has been done by Greet Hofstede (1980 and 1983). He surveyed more than 116,000 IBM managers and employees in 40 countries and found they tend to vary on five value dimensions of national culture:

1.Power distance. The degree people in a country accept that power in institutions, organizations, and societies is unequal. It ranges from relatively equal (low power distance) to extremely unequal (high power distance).

2.Individualism versus Collectivism. Individualism is a cultural attribute with a loose social framework in which people look out for and care mostly for themselves.

3.Masculine versus Feminine. Masculinity pertains to a cultural value in which social gender roles are clearly distinct. Men are expected to be assertive, tough, and focused on material success. Women are expected to be sweet, kind, and motherly.

4.Uncertainty avoidance. In cultures with strong uncertainly avoidance, people come across as busy, fidgety, emotional, aggressive, and active. In cultures with weak uncertainly avoidance, people give the impression of being quiet, easy-going, and patient.

5.Long-term versus Short- term. People in cultures with a long-term orientations look to the future and value thrift and persistence. A short-term orientation values the past and present. It emphasizes respect for tradition and tends to seek instant gratification.

These differences have been helpful in explaining and predicting behavior of employees from various countries.(see table below) For example, in terms of Japanese and American and Thais citizens, Americans are socialized to be individualistic. In contrast, Japanese and Thai are indoctrinated with “team play” and to work in groups. American education is to learn to think, analyze and ask questions. Japanese and Thai, on the other hand, tend to prefer to listen, trust, receive orders and work as a team. The Thais tend to be even more passive them the Japanese. The average US worker is more competitive and self focused than the Japanese worker. Thais worker tend to take less initiative than the Japanese. He wants to think for himself and does not want to blindly follow orders. Japanese and Thai employees prefer not to stand out from the group and want to be rewarded as a group ordinarily. These differences in socialization practices have significantly different results in each country’s employees.

Table 1.Examples of Types of Stress

Physical properties of the working environment
Physical hazards, chronic dangers
Extremes of heat. cold, humidity, pressure, etc.
Bad man-machine design
Time variables
Non-standard working hours (shift work)
Deadlines
Time pressure
Social and organizational properties of work and its setting
Work-load. overload
Responsibility load

Monotony Poor labour- management relations Changes in job Qualitative changes in job Overpromotion Transfer of job focus Null changes (non-events) Role related
Role ambiguity Role conflict Role strain Degree of control over work processes Responsibility for people Miscellaneous Job complexity, qualitative load Quantitative overload or underload Relationship to supervisor Inadequate support from or performance by supervisors Ambiguity about future, job insecurity Monotony Person- environment (job) fit Role ambiguity responsibility for people Job complexity Off-job stress Disturbed life pattern of miscellaneous stresses Stressful life events Demands of husband and children on working women

Source: adapted from Holt (1993).

3. The Impact of Stress on Individuals

Individuals are continuously exposed to stressful occurrences in their day to day life. Completing deadlines, excessive demands of work, long meetings, changing business conditions, political interference, business demands etc are some stressful situations responsible for imbalances in the mental, physical and emotional state

of the individual's life. Sometimes individual fail to recognize the deteriorating conditions of their overall health, Symptoms like headache, migraine, forgetfulness, irritations, tiredness, sleeplessness, fatigue are all results of pressures faced by them⁴. Signs of stress can be noticed in the way an individual acts, thinks and feels such as:-Inability to deal with small and petty problems.

Feel frustration and, losing temper more often, and yelling at others for no reason.

Feeling fatigue all the time difficulty in focusing on task an unnecessary worries for small things are emotional responses to stress How stress affects an individual differs from person to person depending upon:-Personality of an individual: is the mediating factor that determines whether the person will feel stressed or not.

Coping with stress: handling stress varies from person to person. Attitudes: reaction to stress whether positive orientation or negative orientation.

. Table -2 Effects of stress.

On your body	On your thoughts and feelings	On your behavior
Headache Back pain Chest pain Heart disease Heart palpitations High blood pressure Decreased immunity Stomach upset Sleep problems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Anxiety ▪ Restlessness ▪ Worrying ▪ Irritability ▪ Depression ▪ Sadness ▪ Anger ▪ Feeling insecure ▪ Lack of focus ▪ Burnout ▪ Forgetfulness 	Overreacting Loss of appetite Angry outbursts Drug or alcohol abuse Increased smoking Social withdrawal Crying spells Relationship conflicts

Suggestions

Stress is an indispensable part of our modern life and if not dealt with it poses a great threat to every individual in a society.

We recommend the following to the librarians to get rid of stress or at least minimize its effect. To deal with individual stress:

1. Individuals have to find the sources of stress.
2. Avoid conditions which cause stress.
3. Try to have control over stress.
4. Improve good relations with people they work with.
5. Try to be calm in all cases.
6. Work in a place where they get job satisfaction.
7. Create a calm and organized working condition.
8. Individuals should not get disturbed at every event.
9. Try to have leisure to do something else.
10. Be thrifty.
11. Go on a holiday when they have time and money.
12. Ask for help from experts or from people they work with.
13. Go over their obligations and give up those they find tedious.
14. Know their limits and confine their expectations within these limits.

To deal with organizational stress:

1. Develop a system of priorities.
2. Say no to works which exceed their capacity.
3. Develop open and effective relations and dialogue with administrators.
4. Be open to debate on the date a work is to be finished.
5. Develop good relations with their colleagues at work.
6. Have good relations with people working under their control.
7. If necessary delegate authority to someone else.
8. Resist demands from top-level administrators which may evoke confrontation with their colleagues.
9. Try to speak with their colleagues or administrators in the event of any misunderstanding about the work they perform.
10. Organization has to determine the source of stress to individuals and try to eliminate it.
11. For good relations among personnel an organization must schedule public relations courses.
12. Individual's obligation and work within an organization must be clearly defined.
13. Emphasis must be put on equipment and infrastructure to increase productivity.
14. Librarians must be subjected to training about the work they perform and taught ways to deal with stress.
15. Librarians must upgrade themselves constantly and if necessary work with assistants to train them.

16. Librarians must be lenient towards each other in extreme working conditions.
17. Personnel must avoid unnecessary argument and confrontation with colleagues.
18. Put limitations to the demands of students and avoid tedious work.
19. Authority confrontation must be avoided (Dinçyürek, 2006).

It is not possible to completely eliminate the causes of stress within an organization. Our aim is not totally eliminating stress. The aim is to be happy in spite of stress and create happy, joyful working conditions within an organization (Dinçyürek, 2006).

4. Impact of Stress Management on Human Competencies

Human Resource staffs are often in the front line in dealing with cases of work-related stress – especially in liaison with line managers and occupational health – and dealing with associated attendance management issues. HR staff are also responsible for the generation and maintenance of many of the relevant policies and procedures that apply to this issue. Good knowledge management relies on people having the right motivation to share and contribute their hunches and observations, even if it's not always what people want to hear or be reminded of.

Huge workload resulted in forgetfulness, irritability, lower productivity, postponed deadlines and spread of such melancholy across the organization. So sources of bad stress can be climate, change, rules, work pace management style, work group characteristics and many other reasons. Similarly bad stress in workplace can be caused by long hours working, repetitive and distasteful tasks, isolations, job hazards, poor public image of organization, lack of job security or any conflicting demands. A successful approach requires that managers be willing looking at organizational stressors as well as employee-directed strategies and programs. The model of stress proposed by Cooper and Marshall, two leading European occupational stress experts, classifies sources of stress as arising from six general areas:

- Stress intrinsic to the job itself (e.g. Too little or too much work, environment, hours, decision-making latitude)
- Role-based stress (Role conflict, role ambiguity, responsibility levels)
- Relationships with colleagues/managers/staff
- Stress around job security and opportunity for career development
- The culture and politics of the organization
- The home-work interface

So, HR staffs are also responsible for the generation and maintenance of many of the relevant policies and procedures that apply to this issue. It is common argument that 'a fit worker is productive worker'.

4. Research Methodology

The materials were examined using a content analysis technique. Content analysis has been described as analysis of the manifest and latent content of a body of communicated materials (as a book, journal and film) through a classification, tabulation and evaluation of its key symbols and themes in order to ascertain its meaning and probable effect. It is a research technique for the objective, quantitative and systematic study of communication content. It involves charting or counting the incidence, or co-incidence or particular items belonging to a set of (normally) predetermined categories. Content analysis has been used for almost a century in many fields, including literature, history, political science, education, psychology and journalism. The language content of the Stress Management was analyzed for responsible employment practices guided by the principles of Stress Management.

4. Conclusion

To manage stress is an imperative for a normal life because we live in times of stress. Stress is caused by a number of sources and we encounter them everywhere. Stress in the workplace is usually connected to stress in our private lives. That is why there has to be a holistic approach to stress

management including both components from work and private life. An assumption that we can live without distress would be very naive. Stress is a feeling produced by an individual in relationship with the environment so it can also be controlled and managed. Stressful situations can be turned to one's profit and kept in the area of a good stress. This case study produced some interesting findings. Higher educational teachers in this case study are well aware of distress and recognize causes of their stress. They are familiar with different physical and psychological signs of distress as well. Research from other foreign (comparable) environments gave rather analogous results. This is hardly surprising, considering that our subjects are highly educated people and stress is nowadays a ubiquity. Burdens of teachers are numerous. Their work requires a lot of expert knowledge, professionalism, research and pedagogical engagement. These jobs lead to a high risk of physical illness and psychological strain. On the organizational level, as noticed within our small sample, activities in this direction are only sporadic and usually not targeted at stress relief. However, we suggest further research focusing on organizational measures that would provide additional valuable information, as well as on how employees interpret these stimuli in the workplace.

Thus, the results of this research cannot be generalized. Considering discussions of Easter by-Smith et al. (2005), in qualitative research, with small patterns and in-depth research of specific phenomena, generalization is not a principal goal. We agree with Gmelch and Burns (1994) too, that academics are all but a homogeneous group of professionals. That is why it would be inappropriate to examine stress without regard to the professional and personal characteristics of individuals. However, findings of this analysis may encourage further research into this topic.

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